

Field campaign June 2024

Aim: Collect field data to improve WP1's model predictions related to the seasonal vertical migration of *Calanus*.

Ship: R/V Helmer Hanssen

Departure: 29th May, morning from Tromsø

Arrival: 3rd June, evening in Tromsø

Study area: Norwegian Sea off Lofoten-Vesterålen, known to host high abundances of *C. finmarchicus*, in June these tend to aggregate at the shelf break, in winter they overwinter in the deep areas offshore (Lofoten basin), during seasonal descent they seem to be concentrated in eddies.

Approach:

1. Sample transect through Hola trench, where the IMR moorings (temporal resolution) are placed and where we have sampled in the last years

- MVP w/ LOPC-CTD-F & ship EK60 (18, 38, 120 kHz) transect
- Stations: CTD-F w/ PAR sensor, water samples for chl *a* & nutrients
Multinet for taxonomy
WP2s/Multinet for *Calanus* samples for lipid pictures, biomass
"Frankenstein"

2. Locate eddy based on SLA and sample this detailed

- MVP transect
- Stations

3. Autonomous platform campaign

Sailbuoy (with EK80 + CT-F + PAR):

Two months of deployment during spring-summer transit.

- 1 May – 1 June (funded by the JPI Oceans CliN-BluFeed project)
- 1 June – 1 July (funded by the NFR Migratory Crossroads project)

The initial deployment is approximately from Røstbanken and include several coastal-to-offshore transects (these requires intense piloting due to traffic). Expecting a slow drift up north towards the shipboard sampling area, where the Seaglider M1 will be deployed alongside the Sailbuoy during the field campaign (see below). The Sailbuoy has an EK80, CT-F & PAR sensor. Both deployment and recovery need to be done using separate vessels.

Seaglider M1 (with EK80 AND/OR UVP6 + CT-F)

It will be deployed only during the field campaign (i.e., deployment and recovery will both happen during the cruise). First, there will be an attempt to make the Seaglider follow the path of the Sailbuoy – thus producing an optical datastream (UVP6) to validate the acoustics. The stability of the Seaglider M1 with both UVP6 + CT-F + EK80 will be tested & evaluated before the cruise. Since the Sailbuoy already has an EK80, in a worse case, Seaglider with UVP6 + CT-F will be used.

Transducer choice

There are two transducer options for the EK80: 200 kHz and 333 kHz. Pierre has rooted for the use of the 200 kHz given, among other things, its broader range. This is still up for the discussion, so talk to Pierre if you have further comments.

4. Other sampling

Multicorer .. for ancient DNA Tristan

Participants

- | | |
|---------------------|-----|
| 1. Sünnje Basedow | UiT |
| 2. Kanchana Bandara | APN |
| 3. Pierre Priou | APN |
| 4. Ehsan Abdi | APN |

4. engineer NN	UiT
5. engineer NN	UiT
6. Camila Serra Pompeii?	DTU-Aqua
7. Florence Rappin	UiT, master student
8. Lorenz Schick	UiT, master student
9. Tristan Cordier	NORCE
10. Sören Hafker	AWI (for CliN-BluFeed)
11. Emilia/Kasia/NN	IOPAN (for CliN-BluFeed)